

Radioligand binding assays for comparison of tau PET probes, PBB3 and T807, in detection of tau pathologies in AD and PSP brains, and neurotoxic tau species in a transgenic mouse model

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1 Introduction

Tau PET enables *in vivo* detection of tau deposits, core lesions in diverse neurodegenerative disorders including Alzheimer's disease (AD) and progressive supranuclear palsy (PSP). Whether different tau tracers detect disease-specific tau deposits of various isoforms and conformers, particularly tau species intimately associated with neurotoxicity remains unclear. We investigated binding properties of tau tracers, [¹¹C]PBB3 and [¹⁸F]T807 (also known as [¹⁸F]AV-1451) in AD and PSP post-mortem brains, and examine the association of *in vitro* and *in vivo* [¹¹C]PBB3 binding with neuronal loss in tau transgenic mouse models.

2 Results and discussion (1)

Binding properties of [¹¹C]PBB3 in AD and PSP brain homogenates

[¹¹C]PBB3 bound to high- and low-affinity sites in the temporal and frontal cortices of an AD patient, where 40% of specific binding was blockable with T807. A single high-affinity [¹¹C]PBB3 site was observed in the motor cortex and basal ganglia of a PSP case, which was not displaceable by T807.

Group	Region	Kd (nM)	Bmax (pmol/g)	BP
AD	Frontal cortex	4.9	3401	690.4
	Temporal cortex	6.3	4303	687.4
PSP	Motor cortex	4.8	589.7	122.5
	Basal ganglia	4.2	554.8	130.6

Competitive binding of PBB3 and T807 against [¹¹C]PBB3 on AD temporal cortex and PSP motor cortex.

Proposed modes of binding sites for PBB3 and T807 on tau fibrils based on the binding curves.

3 Results and discussion (2)

[¹¹C]PBB3-PET for tau pathologies and MRI in rTg4510 mice

Higher [¹¹C]PBB3 binding and reduced volume were found in the neocortex and hippocampus of rTg4510 mice (7-10 months, n=5) compared to age-matched wild-type (n=7). (A, B) PET images at 60-90 min after i.v.; (C,D) MRI scan at 7T; (E) Time-activity curves for [¹¹C]PBB3; (F) PBB3 and AT8 staining for tau lesions on rTg4510 brain sections.

Correlation of *in vitro* and *in vivo* [¹¹C]PBB3 binding with forebrain atrophy

- [¹¹C]PBB3 bound to the forebrain of rTg4510 (A) and brainstem of PS 19 mice (B) with affinity similar to that in human AD and PSP brains, but with reduced number of binding sites.

- Robust correlation was found among *in vivo*, *in vitro* [¹¹C]PBB3 binding and regional atrophy in the forebrain of rTg4510 mice (C, D).

References:

1. Maruyama et al Neuron 2013 79(6): 1094-110

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4 Conclusion

- Our results indicate distinct mode of binding of PBB3 and T807 to multiple sites on tau fibrils which varies among AD, PSP brain.

- The intimate correlation between [¹¹C]PBB3 binding and regional atrophy in rTg4510 mice supports the ability of [¹¹C]PBB3 to detect neurotoxic tau species in both *in vitro* and *in vivo* assays.

- Furthermore, multiple tau tracer imaging would potentially clarify regional distribution of tau strains and their contributions to localized neuronal loss, focal signs, rate of disease progression and targeted therapy toward specific tau species.

5 Methods

Homologous and heterologous competitions of [¹¹C]PBB3 and [¹⁸F]T807 binding with unlabeled PBB3 and T807 were assayed with homogenates of the brains of AD (3R+4R tauopathy), PSP (4R tauopathy) and control subjects and 4R P301L (rTg4510) and P301S (PS19) mutant tau transgenic mice. [¹¹C]PBB3-PET and MRI were carried out in rTg4510 (n = 5) and wild-type (n = 7) mice aged 7-10 months, followed by *in vitro* binding and fluorescence analyses¹.

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